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INFLUENCE OF ACCESSIBILITY AND CULTURAL BELIEF ON UTILIZATION OF PRIMARY HEALTHCARE SERVICES AMONG HEALTH CONSUMERS IN GOMBE STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of accessibility and cultural belief on utilization of primary health care services among health consumers in Gombe State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the conducts of the study. Descriptive research design of survey type was adopted for the study. Five research questions and five null hypotheses were used. The population for the study was one million, one hundred and thirty-eight thousand, six hundred and fifty seven. (1,138,657), comprised of the entire adult male and female health consumers in Gombe state, who attended all primary health care centers from October to December 2019. A sample of 400 respondents was selected using a multi – stage sampling technique. A self-developed questionnaire named “Influence of accessibility and cultural belief on Utilization of Primary Health Care Services Among Health Consumers in Gombe State (IACBUPHC SHCGS)”.was used as instrument for data collection with the reliability coefficient correlation of 0.79 which was obtained using split-half and Spearman’s Brown Prophecy formula was used. The result of the study revealed that, Accessibility to primary health services is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary Healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe (χ^2 cal. Value was 13.091 at $df = 1$ and $p < 0.05$); Cultural belief is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare among health consumers in Gombe State (χ^2 cal. Value was 78.222 at $df = 1$ and $p < 0.05$); Findings of the study revealed that Accessibility of health services and cultural belief are significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. It was recommended among others that government should improve measures to encourage healthcare consumers in other to utilization of primary healthcare services.

KEYWORDS: Influence, Accessibility, Cultural Belief, Health Consumers, Gombe State

INTRODUCTION

The Primary Health Care (PHC) system is the first level of contact for the healthcare seeker. It is the bed rock of the national healthcare system. Nigeria adopted PHC as the corner stone of her national health care system and a priority for national development in 1986 and after decades, the primary health care still lacks the capacity to achieve its objective (Aregbeshola, & Khan, 2017). Health of the people in the country as well as maternal and child health status become important indicators for socio- economic development (Azuh, Chinedu & Azuh, 2017). The International Conference on Primary Health Care (PHC) defined primary health care as an essential health care based on practical, scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally accessible to individuals and their families in the community through their full participation and at a cost that community and country can afford to maintain at every stage of their development in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination (World Health Organization, 1978). The goal of PHC was to provide accessible health for all by the year 2000 and beyond. Consequently, to achieve this goal, the National Health Policy, brought a comprehensive health care system based on primary health care regulations (Federal Ministry of Health, 1987). The main objective is to promote, protect, prevent, restore and rehabilitate all citizens within the context of available resources. As a result, individuals and communities are assured of productivity, social well-being and enjoyment of living.

Accessibility can be viewed from different points of view such as availability of services, transport costs to obtain service or the distance or state of road to be travelled. Where there is good access, there is usually a corresponding increase in utilization. Good access to primary health facilities in Vietnam with the average distance from provider to client being 1.85km and a travel time of twenty minutes has encouraged utilization; distance was therefore not perceived as a barrier to health service utilization (Duong, Binns & Lee, 2004; Chen, Kazayian & Wrong, 2008). In Nepal, it was observed that clients who lived greater than 2km from the primary health clinics had low utilization of health facilities and will seek maternal health services such as deliveries at home (Yadav, 2010). Availability will usually lead to high utilization as seen in rural villages of Pakistan, because of the availability of different health centres, 93% of respondents had utilized provided services (Rehman, Khan & Abbas, 2007). Long distances, lack of funds for transportation and lack of a transport system are reasons given by 68%, 54% and 77% of respondents for non-utilization of health care services in a middle belt Nigerian state, Rivers state. These same reasons were cited as the reason for non-utilization in southwestern Nigeria (Adeyemo, 2005).

Transportation is a significant problem in rural areas where public transportation systems do not exist. Information gathered indicated that, even in urban area, the timelines and convenience of public transportation affects access to health care. An area can be disputed as underserved if the nearest source of care is greater than 30 minutes away from the primary health care services. Transportation availability, travel distance to healthcare facility, possession of driver's license and a care also determine an individual availability to access health care. A negative relationship between distance to a healthcare facility and number of chronic and regular care visits for adults has been observed (Kabiru, Iliasu, Abubakar & Sani, 2005). Omeregha and Antigha (2018) observed that generally health care utilization limited to Akpabuyo Local Government Area of Cross River and other studies

have attributed access to many reasons, for instance long distance to healthcare facilities has long been established as one of the barriers to healthcare utilization, and such physical barriers to accessing

healthcare facilities have also been implicated as a determinant of child mortality in rural Akpabuyo. Onokerhoaye (1999) further asserted that lack of healthcare facilities over the years have brought about the transportation problem experience and its attendant cost.

In developing countries such as South Africa, the effect of distance on services use becomes stronger when combined with the dearth of transportation and poor roads which contributes towards increase cost of visits (Islam & Tahi, 2002; Yunus et.al, 2017). Availability of transport, physical distance of the facility and time taken to reach the facility has been shown to influence health care utilization. It has also been reported that the distance separating patients and clients from the nearest facility has been remarked as an important barrier to use primary or community health care facilities, especially in rural area (Shaikh & Hatcher, 2004; Krishnawamy et al, 2009). The current study showed that in terms of distance, the clinics were accessible as most of the participants lived within 5km of such facility. According to the set norms and standard of the South Africa PHC services, access is measured by the proportion of people living within 5km of a clinic (Yadav, 2010). Cultural beliefs such as reduced exposure to medical care in early pregnancy; ingestion of herbs and use of traditional birth attendants were seen as means of protecting and preserving the unborn child in a community in South Africa (Ngomane & Mulaudzi, 2010). Shared culture and language facilitate information sharing and influence service utilization within communities, sharing same language even in a multi ethnic setting usually will affect utilization through shared experience sharing as shown in Canada while studying some of the immigrant population (Deri, 2009). In Nigeria, ethnicity is an important influencer of utilization of health services; certain tribes in the south, east and middle belt region are more likely to use maternal health services than their counterparts in the northern parts of the country (Babalola & Fatusi, 2010).

Culture is a complex term referring to value, practice, meanings, and beliefs which are transmitted from one person to another through the process of enculturation, culture, often considered a barrier to health care services, can influence knowledge and beliefs of illness as well as the course of treatment for illness. Interacting with culture, social networks can also cue an individual to utilize or abstain from health services and can function identification of illness and illness response (Kefeli & Zaidi, 2013). Ikels (2002) observes that culture shapes not only illness treatment but also illness recognition, perception of illness severity, and confidence the efficacy of specific treatment for illnesses. For example, in many cultures, dementia in elderly is viewed as a normal process of ageing's; thus it does not necessitate medical care. As such, variance in health care utilization can result due to cultural knowledge and understanding of illness. Umunna (2015) stipulated that beyond faith in efficacy, culture can have differing notions of the self which may influence health service utilization for instance, in the United State as well as many other Western countries, there are two main conceptions of self, one that is autonomous and one that is heteronymous.

Multiple factors influence the utilization of primary health care in Gombe state. These are sustainability of donor- funded health interventions as effectiveness of lost, suitability for the skills and attitude of health workers and potential for adaptation to different local concept (Scheirer and Dearing,2011). Actions taken when interventions are introduced are also important, such as planning

for sustainability from the outset, building relationship with stakeholder groups and harnessing powerful champions' support as well as ensuring interventions are institutionalized within host health system rather than existing in parallel, (Shelton, Cooper & Stirman, 2018).

- **Research Questions**

The following research questions were formulated to guide the conduct of the study:

1. Is accessibility to health facility a factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State?
2. Is cultural belief a factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State?

- **Hypotheses**

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. Accessibility to health facility is not significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State
2. Culture is not a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

- **Conceptual Framework**

A conceptual framework provides a structured explanation of the relationships among key variables in a study and illustrates how these variables interact to explain a given phenomenon (Smyth, 2004). In the present study, the conceptual framework is developed to explain the relationship between accessibility to healthcare services, cultural beliefs, and the utilization of healthcare services among healthcare consumers in Gombe State, Nigeria.

In this framework, utilization of healthcare services represents the dependent variable, while accessibility factors and cultural belief factors constitute the independent variables. Accessibility factors include distance to healthcare facilities, availability of healthcare services, cost of care, and availability of healthcare personnel. Cultural belief factors encompass traditional health practices, religious beliefs, family influence, and prevailing community norms. These factors are assumed to significantly influence individuals' decisions regarding when, how, and whether to utilize formal healthcare services.

The framework further acknowledges that healthcare utilization is influenced by broader **social contexts**, particularly family and community structures. Families and community members play a critical role in shaping health-seeking behaviour through shared beliefs, advice, experiences, and social expectations. These social influences interact with both accessibility and cultural belief factors to either promote or discourage the use of modern healthcare services.

Figure 1 illustrates the interaction between the independent variables (accessibility to healthcare services and cultural beliefs) and the dependent variable (utilization of healthcare services). The framework assumes that improved accessibility and positive cultural perceptions of modern healthcare will enhance the utilization of healthcare services. Conversely, poor access to healthcare

facilities and restrictive cultural beliefs are likely to reduce the level of healthcare utilization among healthcare consumers in Gombe State.

PASCHAL, O. N (2024) MODEL

This conceptual framework therefore provides a logical structure for understanding the factors influencing healthcare utilization in Gombe State and guides the selection of variables, data collection, and analysis in the study.

➤ **Influence of Accessibility on the Utilization of Primary Health Care Services**

The importance of geographical accessibility to healthcare services cannot be overemphasized. Several studies have established that distance to health facilities and travel time constitute major barriers to healthcare utilization, particularly in developing countries (Hjorisberg & Mwikisa, 2002; Hjorisberg, 2003). Long distances, poor transportation systems, and high transportation costs significantly discourage individuals from seeking timely healthcare services.

In many rural and economically disadvantaged areas, especially in developing countries, road networks are often poorly developed or completely absent. Good road infrastructure is essential not only to enable individuals to access health facilities but also to facilitate the effective distribution of drugs and medical supplies, ensure prompt referral of patients during emergencies, and allow adequate supervision of healthcare workers. Where such infrastructure is lacking, access to healthcare services becomes severely limited.

In addition, inadequate communication facilities further restrict access to healthcare services. This challenge is particularly pronounced in remote communities where communication networks are often disrupted during adverse weather conditions. In such settings, patients and healthcare providers may be unable to communicate effectively, thereby delaying medical interventions.

Furthermore, the remoteness of health centres increases both the time and financial costs associated with seeking care. Transportation expenses, accommodation costs, and loss of productive time

collectively serve as significant barriers to healthcare utilization, especially among low-income populations. As a result, limited accessibility disproportionately affects the poor and vulnerable groups, leading to reduced utilization of primary healthcare services.

➤ **Influence of Cultural Beliefs on the Utilization of Primary and Hospital Healthcare Services**

Culture encompasses shared values, beliefs, norms, and practices that are transmitted from one generation to another through the process of enculturation. Cultural beliefs play a crucial role in shaping individuals' understanding of health, illness, and healthcare-seeking behavior. While culture has often been perceived as a barrier to healthcare utilization, it also serves as a framework through which individuals interpret symptoms, recognize illness, and decide on appropriate treatment options. Cultural beliefs influence not only perceptions of illness but also decisions regarding the type and source of treatment. Social networks within cultural settings can either encourage or discourage the use of formal healthcare services. These networks often play a key role in identifying illness, interpreting symptoms, and determining appropriate responses to health challenges.

Ikels (2002) observed that culture shapes illness recognition, perceptions of illness severity, and confidence in the effectiveness of specific treatment options. For example, in some cultures, certain health conditions such as dementia among the elderly are regarded as a normal part of ageing rather than a medical condition requiring professional intervention. Consequently, such beliefs may lead to reduced utilization of healthcare services.

Similarly, Gains (1992) noted that beyond beliefs in treatment efficacy, cultural conceptions of the self significantly influence healthcare utilization. In many Western societies, including the United States, two dominant conceptions of the self exist: the autonomous self and the heteronomous self. Kleinman (1980) and Ikels (2002) argued that individuals from cultures that emphasize a heteronomous conception of the self are more likely to rely on family members or social networks in making health-related decisions. In such contexts, treatment choices are often determined collectively rather than individually.

Conversely, in cultures that prioritize autonomy, individuals are more likely to make independent decisions regarding their health and seek professional healthcare services on their own initiative. In these settings, health workers and social health practitioners play an important role in providing information and guidance to support informed decision-making and promote appropriate healthcare utilization.

Overall, cultural beliefs significantly shape patterns of healthcare utilization by influencing perceptions of illness, decision-making processes, and interactions with healthcare providers. Understanding these cultural dynamics is therefore essential for improving access to and utilization of primary and hospital healthcare services.

• **Theoretical Framework**

The utilization of healthcare services is a complex behavioural phenomenon influenced by a combination of individual, social, cultural, economic, and structural factors. In many developing

societies, including Nigeria, healthcare decision-making is strongly shaped by socio-cultural norms, patriarchal structures, religious beliefs, and community networks. These factors interact with the availability and accessibility of healthcare services to determine whether, when, and how individuals seek formal medical care.

Several theoretical models have been developed to explain patterns of healthcare utilization. According to Andersen and Newman (2005), health service utilization can be understood as a form

of individual behaviour influenced by both personal characteristics and contextual factors. Prominent theoretical models in the literature include Parsons' Sick Role Theory (1951), Rosenstock's Health Belief Model (1994), Young's Choice-Making Model (1981), and Andersen's Health Behavioral Model (Rebhan, n.d.). Each of these models provides useful perspectives on healthcare-seeking behaviour.

However, among these theories, Andersen's Health Behavioral Model is particularly relevant due to its comprehensive explanation of healthcare utilization from a socio-demographic, economic, and structural standpoint. The model integrates individual characteristics, enabling resources, and perceived or evaluated health needs, making it well suited to the objectives of the present study. Consequently, this study adopts Andersen's Health Behavioral Model as its theoretical foundation.

➤ **Andersen's Health Behavioral Model**

Andersen's Health Behavioral Model, originally developed in 1968, posits that an individual's use of healthcare services is determined by a combination of personal and contextual factors. The model groups these determinants into three major categories: predisposing characteristics, enabling characteristics, and need-based characteristics. Together, these components explain variations in healthcare utilization across individuals and populations.

1. Predisposing Characteristics

Predisposing characteristics refer to individual attributes that influence a person's likelihood of using healthcare services prior to the onset of illness. These characteristics shape health-related attitudes and beliefs and include:

- a. **Demographic factors**, such as age, sex, and parity;
- b. **Social structure factors**, including educational attainment, occupation, and social class;
- c. **Attitudinal and belief factors**, which encompass health beliefs, values, and perceptions about the effectiveness of modern medical care.

Individuals who believe strongly in the effectiveness of medical treatment and preventive care are more likely to utilize healthcare services than those who rely primarily on traditional or informal care systems (Rebhan, n.d.; Andersen & Newman, 2005).

2. Enabling Characteristics

Enabling characteristics refer to the resources that make healthcare utilization possible. Even when individuals are predisposed to seek healthcare, actual utilization may not occur without adequate enabling resources. These resources exist at both the family and community levels.

At the family level, enabling factors include household income, health insurance coverage, and place of residence. Income determines the ability to afford healthcare costs such as consultation fees, medications, and transportation.

At the community level, enabling resources include the availability, accessibility, and distribution of healthcare facilities, healthcare personnel, and supporting infrastructure. Communities with better-equipped health facilities, shorter travel distances, and adequate staffing levels tend to record higher utilization of healthcare services. Additionally, whether a community is rural or urban influences healthcare utilization due to differences in infrastructure, cultural practices, and access to information (Andersen & Newman, 2005).

3. Need-Based Characteristics

Need-based characteristics represent the most immediate determinants of healthcare utilization. These include both perceived need and evaluated need. Perceived need refers to an individual's subjective assessment of their health status and severity of illness, while evaluated need is based on professional medical diagnoses and clinical assessments by healthcare providers (Rebhan, n.d.; Burgard, 2004; Andersen & Newman, 2005).

Perceived need often serves as the primary trigger for healthcare-seeking behaviour, as individuals respond to symptoms, discomfort, or perceived health risks. Prior illness experiences, health knowledge, and personal preferences further influence how individuals interpret health problems and decide whether to seek medical care.

Figure 1: Anderson's Behavioural Model of Health Service Utilization

Application of Andersen's Model to the Study

In the context of this study, Andersen's Health Behavioral Model provides a useful framework for understanding the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State, Nigeria. The model explains how predisposing characteristics, enabling factors, and need-based factors jointly influence healthcare-seeking behaviour among healthcare consumers.

Predisposing factors such as age, level of education, gender, and previous health experiences shape individuals' awareness, beliefs, and attitudes toward modern healthcare services. For instance,

empirical evidence suggests that women generally utilize healthcare services more frequently than men due to reproductive health needs and greater interaction with the healthcare system.

Enabling factors such as household income, availability of health facilities, distance to healthcare centres, and availability of healthcare personnel determine whether individuals can translate their healthcare needs into actual service utilization. Improved access to modern healthcare services and increased educational opportunities, particularly for women, have enhanced awareness and acceptance of modern medical care, thereby increasing utilization rates (Natai, Islam, Chowdhury, Bari, & Akhter, 2003).

Overall, Andersen's Health Behavioral Model effectively captures the interaction between individual, social, and structural determinants of healthcare utilization, making it an appropriate and robust theoretical framework for this study.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The survey design involves the use of structured questionnaires to collect data from a sample that represents the study population. This design was considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to systematically obtain information on the factors influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State.

The population of the study comprised adult male and female health consumers who utilized primary healthcare (PHC) centres in Gombe State between October and December 2019, as documented in the annual report of the Gombe State Primary Healthcare Development Agency. According to the agency's report, a total of 1,138,657 health consumers accessed PHC services within this period (Gombe State Primary Healthcare Development Agency Report, 2020).

A sample size of 400 respondents was selected for the study. This sample size was considered adequate based on the recommendation of Krejcie and Morgan (1970), who suggested that for a population of 1,000,000 and above, a minimum sample size of 384 respondents is sufficient to ensure representativeness. Therefore, the selected sample size was deemed appropriate for the study.

The multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select the study sample. First, stratified sampling was used to divide Gombe State into its three senatorial zones, namely Gombe North, Gombe Central, and Gombe South. All three senatorial zones were included in the study to ensure adequate geographical representation.

Next, a simple random sampling technique was used to select one local government area from each senatorial zone. This was achieved by writing the names of the local government areas in each zone

on pieces of paper, folding them, placing them in a container, and randomly picking one from each zone. To further narrow the scope of the study, simple random sampling was again used to select three (3) primary healthcare centres from each selected local government area using the same balloting method.

A proportionate sampling technique was applied to determine the number of respondents drawn from each selected primary healthcare centre, based on the population of health consumers who accessed services during the three-month period. This technique was adopted to ensure fair representation of subgroups within the population, particularly where differences in population size existed.

Finally, an availability (convenience) sampling technique was used to select respondents at the point of service delivery in each selected primary healthcare centre until the required sample size of 400 respondents was achieved.

The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled “*Factors Influencing the Utilization of Primary Health Care Services among Health Consumers in Gombe State Questionnaire (IFUPHCSHCGSQ)*”. The questionnaire was structured using a four-point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was subjected to expert review by five lecturers from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education, Bayero University, Kano. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the instrument.

The reliability of the instrument was established using the split-half method, which yielded a reliability coefficient of $r = 0.79$, indicating that the instrument was sufficiently reliable for the study. A total of 400 copies of the questionnaire were administered, out of which 380 copies were correctly completed and returned, representing a high response rate and were subsequently used for data analysis.

For data analysis, simple frequency counts and percentages were used to describe and summarize the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Inferential statistics using the Chi-square (χ^2) test were employed to test the two stated hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

FINDINGS

Hypothesis 1: Accessibility of healthcare service is not significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State.

Table 1: χ^2 Summary of Accessibility as a factor influencing utilization of PHC

	FO	FE	χ^2	df	P
Agree	234	198	13.091	1	0.001
Disagree	162	198			
Total	396				

$\chi^2_{\text{tab}} = 384; df = 1 (p < 0.05)$

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents agreed that accessibility of health facility is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. The table also explains the χ^2 value of 13.091 at df 1 and $p < 0.05$, which simply means that accessibility of health facility is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Cultural believe is not a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services among health consumers in Gombe State.

Table 2: χ^2 Summary of Cultural believe as a factor influencing utilization of PHC

	FO	FE	χ^2	df	P
Agree	286	198	78.222	1	0.001
Disagree	110	198			
Total	396				

$\chi^2_{\text{tab}} = 384; df = 1 (p < 0.05)$

Table 2 Shows that most of the respondents agreed that cultural believe is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. The table also explains the χ^2 value of 78.222 at df 1 and $p < 0.05$, which simply means cultural believe is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study reveal that accessibility of health facilities is a significant determinant of the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. A substantial proportion of respondents agreed that the ease of reaching health facilities influences whether primary healthcare services are utilized. This finding suggests that distance, transportation availability, and physical access remain critical factors affecting healthcare-seeking behaviour among health consumers in the state.

This result is consistent with the findings of Yadav (2010), who reported that in Nepal, clients residing more than two kilometres away from primary health clinics demonstrated low utilization of health facilities and were more likely to seek maternal health services, such as delivery, at home. Similarly, the study aligns with Rehman, Khan, and Abbas (2007), who observed that improved accessibility to health centres in rural villages of Pakistan led to increased utilization, with about 93% of respondents reporting use of available healthcare services.

Furthermore, the findings support the study by Adeyemo (2005), who found that long distances to health facilities, lack of funds for transportation, and absence of an organized transport system were major reasons for non-utilization of healthcare services among respondents in a Middle Belt Nigerian state. These barriers highlight the critical role of infrastructural and economic factors in shaping healthcare utilization patterns.

The results also corroborate the findings of Omeregha and Antigha (2018), who reported that long distance to healthcare facilities has long been established as a major barrier to healthcare utilization.

Their study in Akpabuyo Local Government Area of Cross River State demonstrated that physical barriers such as distance significantly limited access to healthcare services, thereby reducing utilization rates. Collectively, these findings emphasize that inadequate accessibility continues to restrict effective utilization of primary healthcare services in both rural and semi-urban settings in Nigeria.

In addition, the study found that cultural beliefs significantly influence the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State, with about 72% of respondents agreeing that cultural factors affect their healthcare-seeking behaviour. This indicates that deeply rooted socio-cultural norms and values play an important role in determining whether individuals utilize formal healthcare services.

This finding is in line with the study by Babalola and Fatusi (2010), who reported that ethnicity and cultural orientation significantly influence health service utilization in Nigeria. According to their findings, certain ethnic groups in the southern, eastern, and Middle Belt regions are more likely to utilize maternal health services compared to their counterparts in northern Nigeria, where traditional beliefs and norms may discourage frequent use of modern healthcare facilities.

Similarly, the findings align with Sackey (2004), who observed that in Ghana, prevailing cultural beliefs attribute illness to spiritual causes such as sin, unfaithfulness, pride, or poor social relationships. Such beliefs strongly influence health-seeking behaviour, as individuals who perceive sickness as spiritually induced may prefer traditional or spiritual remedies over orthodox medical care. This perception significantly affects the choice and utilization of healthcare services.

Overall, the discussion highlights that both accessibility and cultural beliefs are critical determinants of primary healthcare utilization in Gombe State. Addressing physical barriers to access and incorporating culturally sensitive health education strategies are therefore essential for improving the utilization of primary healthcare services and achieving better health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Accessibility to health facilities is a significant factor influencing the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. The availability of nearby healthcare centres, good road networks, and transportation options plays a crucial role in determining whether health consumers utilize primary healthcare services.
2. Cultural beliefs significantly influence the utilization of primary healthcare services in Gombe State. Traditional norms, values, and belief systems affect healthcare-seeking behaviour and often determine the choice between modern healthcare services and alternative forms of treatment.

• Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Primary healthcare facilities should be established closer to communities, particularly in rural areas, and supported with accessible road networks to enhance physical access to healthcare

services. In addition, functional ambulances and emergency hotlines should be made readily available to ensure timely transportation of patients during emergencies.

2. Regular public enlightenment and health education programmes should be intensified to educate the populace on the importance of utilizing primary healthcare centres as the first point of contact when ill. Such programmes will help reduce reliance on unorthodox practices and harmful cultural beliefs, improve utilization of primary healthcare services, and minimize unnecessary pressure on secondary and tertiary healthcare institutions.

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